

Phytochemical investigation of *Citrus sinensis* flavedo variety Blood Red

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Abstract · Phytochemical examination of *Citrus sinensis* flavedo var. Blood Red resulted in the isolation of seven compounds characterized as methyl tritriacontanoate, methyl triacontanoate, pentacosanoic acid, nobiletin, sinensetin, 5,4'-dihydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxy flavanone 3-O- β -glucoside and glucose.

Keywords : *Citrus sinensis*, Rutaceae, nobiletin, sinensetin, 5,4'-dihydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxy flavanone 3-O- β -glucoside

Introduction

Citrus sinensis (L.) Osbeck var Blood Red (syn *C. aurantium* L var *sinensis*) belongs to Rutaceae family¹ and commonly known as sweet orange or mosambi. It is generally believed that sweet orange in its present form had developed in China, before it migrated to India during the thirteenth century². Sweet oranges are of great economic importance and most widely cultivated all over the world³. The plant is known to have very high medicinal value. It is known to cure skin, dental and oral diseases⁴. Its fruit is strengthening, cardiotoxic, laxative, anthelmintic and removes fatigues. It possesses anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties⁶. In absence of chemical examination of its flavedo, we have undertaken the present investigation.

Results and discussion

Flavedos (2 kg) of variety Blood Red were collected from Department of Horticulture, CCS HAU, Hisar, Haryana, India. The dried flavedos were chopped into small pieces and then extracted with hot methanol. The extract was concentrated over water bath under reduced pressure to obtain viscous mass. The viscous mass thus obtained was mixed with silica gel (60–120 mesh), dried on water bath and subjected to silica gel (60–120 mesh) column chromatography with solvents of increasing polarity and seven compounds were isolated.

Methyl tritriacontanoate (1) It was obtained by using the elutate benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 9). It was crystallized out from methanol as a colourless waxy solid, 6

mg, m p 80 °C (lit⁷ m p 80–82 °C), IR ν (nujol) 802, 1022, 1098, 1262, 1262, 1464, 1738, 2849, 2918 cm⁻¹, ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.59 (3H, s, -COOCH₃), 2.25 (2H t, *J* 7.5 Hz, -CH₂-COO-), 1.18–1.33 (60H, m, 30 $\times$ CH₂), 0.89 (3H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, -CH₂-CH₃). GCMS *m/z* (% abundance) 508 (M⁺, 24), 462 (34), 434 (36), 416 (100), 330 (72), 324 (74).

Methyl triacontanoate (2) The compound was obtained on elution with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 9). It crystallized out from methanol, 8 mg, m p 70 °C (lit⁸ m p 71 °C), IR ν (nujol) 800, 1017, 1029, 1260, 1461, 1732, 2916, 2961 cm⁻¹, ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.60 (3H s, -COOCH₃), 2.47 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, -CH₂-COO-), 0.90–2.00 (54H, m, 27 $\times$ CH₂), 0.94 (3H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, -CH₂-CH₃), GCMS *m/z* (% abundance) 466 (M⁺, 14), 436 (14), 370 (23), 330 (100), 174 (35).

Pentacosanoic acid (3) Elution with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1) afforded this compound. It crystallized out from the methanol, 18 mg, m p 77 °C (lit⁹ m p 78.5–79 °C), IR ν (nujol) 722, 802, 1096, 1261, 1465, 1706, 2849, 2918, 3420 cm⁻¹, ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.81 (3H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, -CH₂-CH₃), 1.18–2.10 (44H, m, 22 $\times$ CH₂), 2.28 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, -CH₂-COO-), GCMS *m/z* (% abundance) 380 (M⁺, 35), 352 (43), 330 (100), 318 (22), 174 (46).

Nobiletin (4) It was obtained on elution with ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 9). It was crystallized out from methanol, 50 mg, m p 135 °C (lit¹⁰ m p 134 °C). It gave

yellow orange colour with Mg/HCl; IR ν (nujol) : 637, 765, 1018, 1215, 1597, 1629, 2841, 2949 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 7.57 (1H, dd, J 7.5, 2.5 Hz, H-6'), 7.48 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-2'), 7.06 (1H, d, J 7.5 Hz, H-5'), 6.63 (1H, s, H-3), 4.10 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.03 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.96 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.93 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.91 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$); GCMS m/z (% abundance) : 402 (M^+ , 100), 372 (28), 330 (13).

Sinensetin (5) : It was obtained on elution with ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 3). It crystallized out from methanol, 18 mg, m.p. 177 °C (lit.¹¹ m.p. 178–179 °C). It gave yellow colour with Mg/HCl; IR ν (nujol) : 767, 1020, 1120, 1333, 1423, 1597, 1651, 2840, 2951 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 4.01 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.96 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.95 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.92 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.90 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.90 (1H, s, H-3), 6.84 (1H, s, J 7.5 Hz, H-5'), 6.59 (1H, s, H-8), 7.01 (1H, dd, J 7.5, 2.5 Hz, H-6'), 7.38 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-2'); GCMS m/z (% abundance) : 372 (M^+ , 100), 330 (31).

5,4'-Dihydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxy flavanone 3-O- β -D-glucoside (6) : It was obtained on elution with methanol-ethyl acetate (1 : 9). It crystallized out from ethyl alcohol, 85 mg, m.p. 210 °C (lit.¹² m.p. 210 °C). Alcoholic ferric chloride gave brown colour. It responded to Mg/HCl test; GCMS m/z (% abundance) : 494 (M^+ , 3), 464 (3), 463 (10), 446 (2), 418 (33), 386 (2), 380 (26), 374 (21), 330 (8), 214 (20), 159 (5), 158 (16), 134 (3), 132 (4), 102 (2); Molish test : positive, Kiliani hydrolysis : glucose, confirmed by direct comparison using paper chromatography. ^1H NMR of glucoside acetate (CDCl_3) : δ 2.02, 2.00, 1.99, 1.97 (3H each, 4s, $4 \times \text{OAc}$), 2.31, 2.26 (3H each, 2s, $2 \times \text{OAc}$), 2.70–5.21 (9H, m, 2C-ring protons, 7 glucose protons), 3.82 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OMe}$), 6.25 (1H, J 2.5 Hz, H-6), 6.40 (1H, J 2.5 Hz, H-8), 7.08 (1H, J 7.5 Hz, H-5'), 7.10 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-2'), 7.19 (1H, dd, J 7.5, 2.5 Hz, H-6').

Glucose (7) : It was obtained on elution with ethyl acetate-methanol (1 : 49), 45 mg, m.p. 148 °C (lit.¹³ m.p. 146–150 °C). It gave positive Liebermann-Burchard reaction. It responded to Molisch test; IR ν (nujol) : 799, 1023, 1074, 1378, 1470, 1641, 2850, 2919, 3365 cm^{-1} ;

^1H NMR of acetate (CDCl_3) δ : 4.29–5.29 (7H, m, 7 sugar protons), 2.11 (3H, s, OAc), 2.10 (3H, s, OAc), 2.01 (3H, s, OAc), 1.98 (3H, s, OAc), 1.95 (3H, s, OAc); GCMS m/z (% abundance) : 182 (M^+ , 3), 178 (100), 147 (52), 111 (23), 97 (39).

Melting points were determined on Ganson Electrical Melting Point Apparatus. ^1H NMR on Bruker AC-400F MHz NMR spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard. IR spectra were obtained on Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer. Mass spectra were recorded on VG-70S 11-250J GC-MS-DS Mass spectrometer.

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